

D7.7 – Mid-term monitoring and evaluation report

WP7 – Management and Coordination

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Delivery date	31/07/2024
Dissemination level	Public

gEneSys

Mid-term Monitoring & Evaluation report

<i>Project Acronym</i>	<i>gEneSys</i>
<i>Agreement number</i>	101094326
<i>Project Full Title</i>	<i>gEneSys - Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems</i>
<i>Funding Scheme</i>	Horizon Europe

Deliverable Information

<i>Deliverable Name</i>	D7.7 – Mid-term monitoring and evaluation report
<i>Dissemination level</i>	Public
<i>Funding Scheme</i>	Horizon Europe
<i>Grant Agreement number</i>	101094326
<i>Deliverable Leader</i>	CNR-IRPPS
<i>WP/Task Responsible</i>	CNR-IRPPS
<i>Keywords</i>	M&E, mid-term

Document history

<i>Date</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Contributor(s)</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Supervision</i>
	1	Serena Tagliacozzo	First draft	n/a
	2	Lucio Pisacane		n/a

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1. INTRODUCTION

The gEneSys Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) strategy was described in D7.3 and elucidated modes and timeframe for the evaluation of the project. The project's M&E is formative and forward looking and pursues the following objectives:

1. Make sure that the project's reports and outputs are delivered as planned and that the stated objectives and deadlines of the project are met.
2. Ensure that the tasks run smoothly and in the full respect of the project's founding principles of transparency, mutual learning, collaboration and valorization of the competencies of all the participants (including senior and junior staff) as declared and agreed among partner organizations during the kickoff meeting (see D 7.1.).
3. Capture emerging phenomena and requests in the wider environment and within the consortium that may warrant a shift in the specific tasks and/or objectives. In this respect, the role of the stakeholders is paramount to stay abreast of the emergent tendencies and disruptions in the energy and green transition arena, which is the area of interest of the gEneSys project.

The current deliverable describes the results of two rounds of evaluation and the next steps/actions to make improvements to the current project's activities and working modes. The deliverable is structured as follows: first we recap the M&E's dimensions and indicators and the modes and timeline for verification. Then we present the results of the evaluation activities.

2. MONITORING AND EVALUATION STRATEGY

2.1. Dimensions and indicators

Based on the above-mentioned objectives, the following M&E dimensions were identified:

EVALUATION DIMENSION 1. *Internal Relationships' Management*

This dimension is intended to gather insights into the functioning of the gEneSys consortium and anticipate and resolve potential bottlenecks induced by conflicts and divergent interests and working practices among partners that may hinder the achievement of the project's objectives. Overall, this M&E dimension seeks to respond to the following evaluation questions:

- (1) How well do participants collaborate by sharing knowledge, information and resources?
- (2) How well is the consortium able to adapt its organisational practices to the changeable circumstances and demands coming from the inside and outside of the network?
- (3) To what extent are participants able to manage conflicts and tensions while remaining respectful of the divergent working practices and organisational priorities?
- (4) How well is the coordinating structure able to manage diversity and heterogeneity within the network?
- (5) How well can the participants manage the individual and shared resources made available by the network (i.e. time, lessons, money, staff)?

- (6) To what extent does the project foster EU integration and international cooperation?
- (7) To what extent have early career researchers been involved in the project activities?

EVALUATION DIMENSION 2. *Internal – Project activities and outputs*

This evaluation dimension gathers information about the extent to which the project objectives are achieved through the delivery of the project’s outcomes and outputs and about the perceptions of partners regarding the project’s implementation. It also takes into consideration the added value of the projects’ outputs for the stakeholders and the society at large. Overall, this evaluation dimension seeks to respond to the following questions:

- (1) Were the project’s outputs delivered on time?
- (2) Did the project’s activities and outputs fulfill the objectives set for the project?
- (3) Did the project’s outputs add new elements to the existing scientific knowledge and policy debate?
- (4) To what extent are the partners and the whole consortium able to translate scientific and technical information into knowledge understandable by policymakers and society at large?
- (5) To what extent have the project’s key themes (e.g. just transition, gendered impacts of energy transition etc.) been mainstreamed into the research of the partner organisations, beyond the gEneSys project?
- (6) To what extent are the resources provided for the project (e.g. budget, time, guidance) perceived as sufficient by partner organisations?

EVALUATION DIMENSION 3 – *External – stakeholder engagement*

This third evaluation dimension explores the extent to which the consortium engages with relevant stakeholders and builds relationships that may help in disseminating project’s results.

- (1) To what extent do partner organisations create new ties with external stakeholders?
- (2) To what extent are the project’s activities and outputs perceived as relevant by the external stakeholders?
- (3) To what extent are the project’s results disseminated among the external stakeholders?
- (4) To what extent are the stakeholders committed to or aligned with sustainable practices and long-term project’s objectives?

Given these dimensions, we established a set of indicators to evaluate each of them. These are summarised in the table below:

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>Questions</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Means of evaluation</i>
1.Internal Relationships’ Management	How well partners collaborate by sharing knowledge, information and resources	1.a Perception of bottlenecks in the sharing of information	Surveys to all the participants

		and resources within the consortium	
	How well is the consortium able to adapt its organisational practices to the changeable circumstances and demands coming from the inside and outside of the network	1.b Perception of responsiveness and adaptability to internal changes	Surveys to all the participants
		1.c Perception of responsiveness and adaptability to external changes and demands	
	To what extent are participants able to manage conflicts and tensions	1.d Frequency to which different working practices created bottlenecks in the project's activities	Surveys to all the participants
	How well is the coordinating structure able to manage diversity and heterogeneity within the network	1.e Perceived ability of the coordinating organization to manage internal relationships	Surveys to all the participants
	How well can the participants manage the individual and shared resources made available by the network (i.e. time, lessons, money, staff)?	1.f Perceived ability to make use of the resources made available within the network	Surveys to all the participants
	To what extent do partners perceive to get benefits from being part of the consortium	1.g Perceived benefits deriving from being part of the consortium	Surveys to all the participants
	To what extent does the project foster EU integration and international cooperation?	1.h Increase of the perceived benefits coming from pan-European cooperation	Surveys to all the participants
		1.i Perceived collaboration/power hierarchies between partners from different European regions	
1.l Perceived integration of non EU-partner in the project's activities			
To what extent have early career researchers been involved in the project activities?	1.m. Number of early career researchers working on project activities	Survey to team leaders	
	1.n. Number of deliverables where an	Review of deliverables	

		early career research appear as author	
		1.o Number of training/networking opportunities for early career researchers	Survey to team leaders
Internal – Project activities and outputs	Were the project’s outputs and tasks delivered on time	2.a Number of deliverables submitted as planned	Review of deliverables and tasks
	Did the project’s activities and outputs fulfill the objectives set for the project?	2.b Number and type of project’s objectives fulfilled by each output	Review of the outputs produced by the project Surveys to advisory board members
	Did the project’s outputs add new elements to the existing scientific knowledge and policy debate?	2.c Perceived added value	Survey to advisory board members
		2.d Number of scientific publications produced	Review of the scientific publications produced
	To what extent is the project consortium able to translate scientific and technical knowledge into information that can be understood and used by policymakers and by the society at large?	2.e Number of policy briefs and policy documents produced	Review of outputs
		2.f Number of materials produced for public outreach	Review of outputs
	To what extent have the project’s key themes (e.g. just transition, gendered impacts of energy transition etc.) been mainstreamed into the research of the partner organisations, beyond the genesys project?	2.g Perceived integration of key themes into other research streams	Survey to team leaders
	To what extent are the resources provided for the project (e.g. budget, time, guidance) perceived as sufficient by partner organisations?	2.h Perceived efficiency of the project	Survey to team leaders
	To what extent do partner organisations	3a Number and type of new connections created outside the consortium	Survey to team leaders

3.External – stakeholder engagement	create new ties with external stakeholders?		
	To what extent are the project’s activities and outputs perceived as relevant by the external stakeholders?	3b Perceived relevance by external stakeholders	Survey to external stakeholders
	To what extent are the project’s results disseminated among the external stakeholders?	3c Number of dissemination activities performed	Survey to team leaders
	To what extent are the stakeholders committed to or aligned with sustainable practices and long-term project’s objectives?	3d Number of meetings, workshops, or conferences attended during the project and at the end.	Excel form to send to all the external stakeholders.
		3e Monitor the extent and tone of media coverage related to the project through social media.	Excel form to send to all the external stakeholders.

2.2. Evaluation modes and timeline

The gEneSys M&E strategy has envisaged three different instruments for the collection of evaluation data:

- 1) **An excel sheet used to track tasks and deliverables** and monitor whether were performed as per proposal (indicator #2a) and which project’s objectives they fulfill (indicator # 2b). In addition, the excel sheet is also used to track the number of scientific publications (indicator 2d) and of documents for policymakers and the public produced during the project (indicator 2e and 2f).

<i>DELIVERABLE NAME</i>	<i>TASK LEADER</i>	<i>DATE OF PLANNED SUBMISSION AS FOR PROPOSAL</i>	<i>SUBMITTED AS FOR TIMELINE? INSERT YES/NO AND DATE OF SUBMISSION</i>	<i>OBJECTIVE FULFILLED</i>	<i>DOES an early career research appear as author</i>
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- 2) **An online survey to collect input from partner organizations.** This survey has been created through the CNR’s Limesurvey account and includes questions for all the participants as well as for team leaders. This survey contains questions regarding working modes, information sharing, the staff working within each team, the type of new ties created by the research group and the research streams beyond the gEneSys project. The survey can be found in Appendix 1 of this document.

2) An online survey to collect input from the advisory board members and the external stakeholders.

Below we report on the envisaged activities and respective timing for the first 18 months of the project, as planned in the M&E strategy.

<i>TIME</i>	<i>ACTIVITY</i>
July 2023	Submission of the M&E strategy.
September 2023	Set-up of the excel sheet and creation of the survey for partners.
end of September 2023	The online survey is sent out to partner organizations. The excel sheet is updated by the M&E team.
24-25 October 2023	Results are discussed in the second steering committee in Berlin.
February 2024	The survey for advisory board members and external stakeholders is created and sent out.
April 2024	The online survey is sent out to partner organizations. The excel sheet is updated by the M&E team.
July 2024	Information collected is summarized in the mid-term evaluation deliverable (D7.7).
September 2024	Results of the second survey are discussed in the third steering committee in Krakow.

The following deviations from the above timeline must be noted:

1. The survey for advisory board and external stakeholders has been designed but not administered yet. This happened because in the first 18 months of the project there were few opportunities for in-person interactions and engagement with advisory board members and stakeholders. On October 22nd 2024, gEneSys will be organizing an in-person conference in Brussels where EU policy officers, relevant academics and advisory board members will be invited to discuss the project's results, outcomes and outputs. On that occasion, relevant contacts will be made, and the people will be reached out to and asked to respond to a few questions about the relevance and innovativeness of the project's ideas and outputs.
2. The third project meeting took place in Krakow in June 2024 so the responses to the second round of partners' survey have already been discussed and are presented in this deliverable.

3. M&E RESULTS

3.1. Survey results

In this section, we comparatively present the results of the two rounds of the M&E survey conducted in October 2023 and June 2024. The two surveys closed one week before respectively the second and the third project meetings held in Berlin and Krakow so it was possible to discuss results with the project's team members.

Figure 1: Results of the question "Since the project's onset, how frequently did you experience bottlenecks in the sharing of information and resources within the consortium?"

Figure 1 shows the perceived bottlenecks in the sharing of information and resources within the consortium. Both in the first and second M&E periods, most of the partners did not perceive any bottleneck, however, seven partners reported having sometimes experienced some bottleneck during the first period, while only four respondents reported having perceived this issue during the second period. In the second M&E period, the number of partners not experiencing bottlenecks increased, while the number of partners sometimes experiencing bottlenecks decreased. In the second period, however, one partner declared to have experienced bottlenecks very frequently.

Figure 2: Results of the question “Since the project’s onset, how frequently did you perceive that different working practices have created bottlenecks in the delivery of the project’s activities?”

Different working practices may cause bottlenecks in the delivery of the project's activities (refer to Figure 2). Although one survey respondent frequently experienced such an issue during the June 2024 survey, the majority indicated that divergent working practices *did not create at all* bottlenecks in either the initial phase (7 respondents) or the subsequent phase (8 respondents). Within the subset of respondents who *sometimes* perceived working practices as impeding project task completion, the incidence of this situation declined from the first survey (8) to the second (5), signifying enhanced coordination in collaborative approaches among project partners.

Figure 3: Results of question “Do you think that the project coordination team (CNR) has been able so far to manage well the relationships among partners (CNR team should skip this question)?”

Excluding the 4 blank responses from CNR team members, interviewees provided positive evaluations of the CNR’s role in managing relations between partners in both the first survey of October 2023 (11 respondents) and the second one of June 2024 (9 respondents).

Figure 4: Results of the question: “Since the project’s onset, did you perceive to be able to take full advantage from the resources made available by the consortium (e.g. funds to attend conferences, opportunities to expand professional networks)?”

When analyzing Figure 4, it was noted that most interviewees indicated full utilization of the project resources. However, distinct trends were observed between the initial and subsequent M&E periods. In the October 2023 survey, 11 respondents confirmed this perception. Conversely, the June 2024 survey revealed a smaller increase in the interviewees expressing limitations in accessing project resources (3: not always, and 1: not), albeit the overall perception remained positive (10: yes). These findings suggest the potential limitations in the use of resources. In general, responses confirmed that being part of the gEneSys consortium enhanced the possibility for team members to engage in scientific events such as conferences and networking opportunities.

Figure 5: Results of question: “For EU partners only: Since the project’s onset, how often did you perceive the benefits coming from pan-European collaboration?”

The opportunities for European partners are related to the benefits perceived from pan-European collaborations (figure 5). While there was a marginal decrease in perceived levels of these benefits between the first and subsequent survey waves, the valence stayed positive. In October 2023, the responses indicated "very frequently" (a total of 5 responses) and "sometimes" (a total of 4 responses). During the subsequent observation period (June 2024), the perceived benefits from pan-European collaboration were frequently credited as such (7 respondents). The decline includes both negative polarities, as evidenced by the absence of responses for "not at all" and 2 responses for "sometimes", and positive polarity, with only 2 indications for "very frequently". A few interviewees, in both surveys, preferred not to provide any answer to this question.

Figure 6: Results of question "Since the project's onset, how often did you perceive that power hierarchies between European regions or with countries outside Europe have influenced the way in which project's activities have been carried out?"

This question aimed to explore how power hierarchies between European regions or with non-European countries are perceived as constraints (figure 6). In the first M&E survey, interviewees reported that they had not encountered such situations (6 responses), while 6 interviewees said it had occurred only occasionally. However, in the second survey in June 2024, the perception of power hierarchies was not perceived at all (8 responses), leading to a decrease in the "sometimes" responses (in total 3). In both surveys, only one respondent perceived these power imbalances as frequent, while two respondents left the question unanswered.

Figure 7: Results of question “For non-EU partners only (e.g., UK and Africa): Since the project’s onset, how often did you perceive that your inputs were not adequately incorporated or valued because of your geographical location?”

This question focused on the perception of how geographical location and political positioning (e.g. not being part of the EU) influenced the valorization of the partners' input, with specific attention to partners from non-European countries such as the UK and Rwanda (see Figure 7). In this regard, only non-EU partners were asked to respond. From the data collected during M&E periods, only one response was recorded in October 2023, for whom there is not this perception at all. In the second survey in June 2024, three respondents confirmed that geographical location or political positioning did not impact the integration of the input they produced. Instead, one respondent indicated that these factors frequently affected the valorisation of the inputs provided. Based on these results, gEneSys coordinators will focus on enhancing the integration of all partners in the project's activities, especially those from non-EU countries.

Figure 8: Results of question "For team leaders only: how many early career researchers work on the project's activities in your team (early career researchers should have no more than three years postdoctoral experience)?"

The bar chart in Figure 8 shows the number of early career researchers working on the project, as reported by team leaders. In three cases there were no early career researchers during the M&E periods. The number of team leaders indicating *one or two researchers* doubled from October 2023 to June 2024. During the October 2023 M&E, only one team leader reported that their team involved *three or more researchers*.

Figure 9: Results of question “For early career researchers only: Since the project’s outputs, how frequently did you perceive that being part of the gEneSys project has offered you training/networking opportunities?”

According to early career researchers (Figure 9), perceptions about the opportunities offered by gEneSys were fairly common. In October 2023, two researchers sometimes acknowledged the project's opportunities, while two others frequently experienced these opportunities. The M&E of June 2024 indicated that the researchers classified the project's opportunities as frequent (2) and very frequent (1). Over the months, working in gEneSys allowed researchers to have opportunities for training and expanding their networks.

Figure 10: Results of question "For team leaders only: Since the project's onset, how frequently did you perceive that the resources provided for the project (e.g., budget, time, guidance) were sufficient to effectively deliver the assigned activities?"

Regarding the resources allocated by the project, team leaders considered them sufficient for carrying out all the assigned activities (figure 10). Perceptions remained consistent from the first M&E period to the second one, except for the response "sometimes", which gained one additional indication in June 2024. Overall, the project resources were frequently and /or very frequently perceived as adequate.

Figure 11: Results of question "For team leaders only: Since the project's onset, how frequently did you perceive that your team has taken advantage of the gEneSys project to create ties with external stakeholders?"

Figure 11 illustrates the frequency distribution regarding team leaders' perceptions of their team's advantage gained from this research context of establishing relationships with external stakeholders. In the October 2023 M&E survey, 5 team leaders indicated that their team had highly frequent stakeholder relationships (3 indications for very frequent and 2 for frequent). This pattern remained almost constant during the June 2024 M&E survey, although in two cases team leaders indicated their team's relationships with external stakeholders had become more occasional (2).

For team leaders only: Since the project's onset, how many opportunities to disseminate project's activities and/or outputs to external stakeholders did you have (e.g., presentation in conferences, running workshops/trainings)?

Regarding dissemination activities within the gEneSys project (Figure 12), team leaders reported a consistent effort in attending conferences, workshops, and training sessions. In detail, dissemination of project results appears to have been concentrated in the period leading up to the October 2023 M&E, with three team leaders attending one or two events and three others attending three or more events. During the June 2024 M&E, most team leaders (four) reported attending one or two events, while only two disseminated results on three or more occasions. This slight decrease for the second M&E period is merely due to the year still in progress, with many more opportunities for participation planned for next autumn, thus not mentioned at the time of the survey.

Figure 13: Results of question “Do you think that the gEneSys consortium is able to respond well to the changing circumstances within the consortium (e.g., new people added)?”

The last bar chart (Figure 13) reports all respondents' assessment of gEneSys' ability to handle changing circumstances within the consortium (such as the entry of new people). In both surveys, respondents agreed that the consortium managed well with every problem that arose.

3.2 Review of project deliverables

Other dimensions of the project, especially those related to the timely delivery of the project's outputs, were monitored by the coordination team through an excel sheet. In particular, the team assessed whether the deliverables were submitted on time and which project's objectives they fulfilled.

The project's objectives are the following:

OBJECTIVE 1. Building the evidence base on structural and cultural forms of discrimination that act as barriers to women's full participation in energy systems (as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, decision makers, citizens and consumers).

OBJECTIVE 2. Identifying who are the power holders, the change actors and the stakeholders who influence the 'greening' agenda through policy/political, technology, environmental, social, and economic instruments, and interventions.

OBJECTIVE 3. Advancing scholarly understanding of how gender equality can be a lever and the outcome of transition to sustainable low-energy world.

OBJECTIVE 4. Advancing scholarly understanding of intersectional aspects of gender equality in 'green' policies, practices, and actions, including implementation of SDG7 targets.

OBJECTIVE 5. Increasing the participation and influence of women in energy transition as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, decision makers, consumers, and citizens.

OBJECTIVE 6. Promoting and facilitating international cooperation between Europe and Africa on dissemination of the evidence base on the importance of gender in energy transition with impact on the UN High level Dialogue on Energy and on implementation of SDGs.

Below here is an overview of the project's deliverable and associated information.

<i>DELIVERABLE NAME</i>	<i>TASK LEADER</i>	<i>DATE OF PLANNED SUBMISSION AS FOR PROPOSAL</i>	<i>SUBMITTED AS FOR TIMELINE ? INSERT YES/NO AND DATE OF SUBMISSION</i>	<i>OBJECTIVE FULFILLED</i>	<i>DOES an early career research appear as author</i>
D1.1 Systematic literature review of studies at the nexus of gender equality and sustainable energy systems and ontology of energy systems	CNR	M8 (30 September 2023)	No 31 October 2023	OBJECTIVES 1 and 3	No
D1.2. Report on Gendered assessment of the energy systems knowledge community and EU policies for sustainable energy systems (Leader: ENEA, M13)	ENEA	M13 (February 2024)	Yes	OBJECTIVES 1, 2 AND 4	Yes
D1.3. A multi-country, comparative, gendered assessment survey of stakeholder organizations in sustainable energy systems	CNR	M15 (April 2024)	No	OBJECTIVES 1, 2, 3 and 4	N/A
D2.1 Report with analytical model	Fraunhofer	M10 (November 2024)	Yes	OBJECTIVE 4	Yes
D. 3.1. Guidance notes for education policy makers on integrating gender perspective into all levels of education on transitions in energy system	UJ	M18 (July 2024)	Yes	OBJECTIVE 1	Yes
D4.1. Report on past and current international cooperation initiatives	AIMS	M14 (March 2024)	Yes	OBJECTIVES 2 AND 6	No

between Europe and Africa					
D5.1. Report on selected indicators for pathways model	IMPERIAL	M18 (July 2024)	No. August 2024	OBJECTIVE 3	N/A
D5.2 Report on gender perspective into energy SHIFTS	IMPERIAL	M12 (January 2024)	Yes	OBJECTIVE 3	No
D6.1. Communication, Dissemination, and Impact strategy	PORTIA	M6 (July 2023)	Yes	n/A	No
D6.2 Review and update of Communication, Dissemination, and Impact strategy	PORTIA	M18 (July 2024)	No. August 2024	n/A	No
D7.1. Programme and summary/outline of project status and decisions taken at the Kick-off meeting	CNR	M2 (March 2023)	Yes	n/A	No
D7.2. Initial data management plan including Protection of Personal Data (POPD)	CNR	M6 (July 2023)	Yes	n/A	No
D7.3. Monitoring and Evaluation strategy	CNR	M6 (July 2023)	Yes	n/A	No
D7.4. First financial report	CNR	M8 (September 2023)	No	n/A	No
D7.5. Second financial report	CNR	M13 (February 2024)	No	n/A	No
D7.6. Programme and summary/outline of the project advancements and decisions taken at the 2nd steering committee meeting	CNR	M14 (March 2024)	Yes	n/A	No
D7.7. Mid-term monitoring and evaluation report	CNR	M18 (July 2024)	No. August 2024	n/A	Yes
D7.9. Final data management plan	CNR	M18 (July 2024)	Yes	n/A	No
D8.1. OEI - Requirement No. 1	CNR	M6 (July 2023)	No	n/A	N/A

As shown above, the greatest part of the project's deliverables was submitted as for proposal. D1.1, D5.1., D6.2, D7.7 have been submitted with few days/weeks of delays. The planned deliverables not

yet submitted were impacted by the delays in the approval process from the CNR ethics committee (see details on the technical report).

In terms of objectives, objective 5 will be pursued by tasks concentrated in the second half of the project. Half of the deliverables containing new analyses or data collected addressed the objective number 1 (*Building the evidence base on structural and cultural forms of discrimination that act as barriers to women's full participation in energy systems*) and/or objective 3 (*Advancing scholarly understanding of how gender equality can be a lever and the outcome of transition to sustainable low-energy world*). This confirms that the first 18 months of the project served the scope of collecting the knowledge base upon which building the subsequent actions and to highlight the role of gender equality in the delivery of just energy transitions.

In terms of early career researchers involved, only few deliverables included researchers with less than 3 years of post-doctoral experience, suggesting the need for a greater involvement of this category.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS AND WAY FORWARD

Based on the above results, the following recommendations are made:

1. The project's teams need to be encouraged to bring up any issues or bottlenecks to the coordination team. The coordination team will be proactive in reaching out to partner organisations to discuss potential issues in collaboration and the delivery of the tasks.
2. Measures should be taken to ensure the full involvement of non-EU partners and early career researchers in the project's activities
3. Outreach and dissemination activities will need to be expanded in the second half of the project, including increasing the presentation of the project's results in scientific conferences and public engagement initiatives. In the first 18 months, the partner organisations have been involved in a series of outreach and dissemination activities which are detailed in the technical report and D6.2. However, opportunities for long-term impacts need to be maximised.

5. ANNEXES

5.1. ANNEX 1: questionnaire for partner organisations

Dear colleagues

This questionnaire is intended to monitor the progresses of the gEneSys consortium from a relational and operational standpoint. As such, it should be considered as an internal tool to capture emerging challenges within the consortium and try to resolve them before that they become detrimental to the project's activities or the project's collaborative climate. Therefore, we kindly ask you to answer the following questions as openly and sincerely as possible. The questionnaire is anonymous so it will not be possible to detect your identity. The participation is voluntary but please consider that your input is critical to improve the consortium's internal dynamics.

The questionnaire is composed of mostly closed-ended questions (please choose only one option per question). At the end of the questionnaire, you can add your free comments in

the text box. Should you have questions or doubts, you can contact Serena Tagliacozzo at this email address serena.tagliacozzo@irpps.cnr.it

Thank you in advance for your co-operation.

Regards

The CNR coordination team

a. Since the project's onset, how frequently did you experience bottlenecks in the sharing of information and resources within the consortium?

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Sometimes
- 3 Frequently
- 4) Very frequently

b. Since the project's onset, how frequently did you perceive that different working practices have created bottlenecks in the delivery of the project's activities?

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Sometimes
- 3 Frequently
- 4) Very frequently

c. Do you think that the gEneSys consortium is able to respond well to the changing circumstances within the consortium (e.g., new people added)?

- 1) yes
- 2) no
- 3) not always

d. Do you think that the gEneSys consortium is able to adapt well to the changing circumstances outside the consortium (e.g., new inputs from emergent research)?

- 1) yes
- 2) no
- 3) not always

e. Do you think that the project coordination team (CNR) has been able so far to manage well the relationships among partners (**CNR team should skip this question**)?

- 1) yes
- 2) no
- 3) not always

f. Since the project's onset, did you perceive to be able to take full advantage from the resources made available by the consortium (e.g. funds to attend conferences, opportunities to expand professional networks)?

- 1) yes
- 2) no
- 3) not always

g. **For EU partners only:** Since the project's onset, how often did you perceive the benefits coming from pan-European collaboration

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Sometimes
- 3 Frequently
- 4) Very frequently

h) Since the project's onset, how often did you perceive that power hierarchies between European regions or with countries outside Europe have influenced the way in which project's activities have been carried out?

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Sometimes
- 3 Frequently
- 4) Very frequently

i) **For non-EU partners only (e.g., UK and Africa):** Since the project's onset, how often did you perceive that your inputs were not adequately incorporated or valued because of your geographical location?

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Sometimes

3 Frequently

4) Very frequently

l) For team leaders only: how many early career researchers work on the project's activities in your team (*early career researchers should have no more than three years postdoctoral experience*)

1) 0

2) one or two

3) three or more

For team leaders only. Since the project's onset, how frequently did the project offer training/networking opportunities for early career researchers

1) Not at all

2) Sometimes

3 Frequently

4) Very frequently

m) For early career researchers only: Since the project's outputs, how frequently did you perceive that being part of the gEneSys project has offered you training/networking opportunities?

1) Not at all

2) Sometimes

3 Frequently

4) Very frequently

n) For team leaders only: Since the project's onset, how frequently did you perceive that the resources provided for the project (e.g., budget, time, guidance) were sufficient to effectively deliver the assigned activities?

1) Not at all

2) Sometimes

3 Frequently

4) Very frequently

o) For team leaders only: Since the project's onset, how frequently did you perceive that your team has taken advantage of the gEneSys project to create ties with external stakeholders?

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Sometimes
- 3 Frequently
- 4) Very frequently

p). For team leaders only: Since the project's onset, how many opportunities to disseminate project's activities and/or outputs to external stakeholders did you have (e.g., presentation in conferences, running workshops/trainings)

- 1) 0
- 2) one or two
- 3) three or more

For team leaders only Since the project's onset, to what extent have the project's key themes (e.g. just transition, gendered impacts of energy transition etc.) been mainstreamed into the research of your organisation, beyond the genesys project?

- 1) Not at all
- 2) To a limited extent
- 3 To some extent
- 4) To a great extent

q) Please use this space for any comments on the aspects touched above

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe - Culture, creativity and inclusive society - under grant agreement no. 101094326